

Research Article

Velocity Approximation of Kuala Lumpur Bus Rides: Weekday vs. Weekend Comparison Using the Discrete Least Squares Method

Zubaidah Sadikin¹, Aina Zulaikha Alauddin², Sidik Rathi³, Nurziana Harun⁴, Muhamad Syahrizam Salidin⁵, Mohd Agos Salim Nasir⁶, and Nurzalina Harun^{7,*}

- 1 Universiti Teknologi MARA Shah Alam; zubaidah1590@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3967-5243
 2 Universiti Teknologi MARA Shah Alam; 2023379931@student.uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0009-0009-0485-447X
 3 Universiti Teknologi MARA Shah Alam; sidik8423@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6408-3920
 4 Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan Seri Selayang; nurzianaharun@gmail.com; ORCID ID: 0009-0001-6687-2843
 5 Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan Seksyen 7 Shah Alam; syahrizamsalidin@gmail.com; ORCID ID: 0009-0006-9157-4684
 6 Universiti Teknologi MARA Shah Alam; mohdagos066@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0000-0002-8761-4595
 7 Universiti Teknologi MARA Shah Alam; nurzalina1587@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0477-580X
 * Correspondence: nurzalina1587@uitm.edu.my; +6019-6553447.

Abstract: This study investigates the application of the Discrete Least Squares Method (DLSM) to approximate and analyze the difference between weekday and weekend traffic flow in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. The data acquisition involved collecting time and distance between each of the 24 stations from the GOKL CityBus route from Titiwangsa to KL Sentral, starting at 1.00 p.m. for each weekday (Thursday) and weekend (Sunday). For weekdays, Thursday represents a normal day without extra traffic jams, like Mondays and Fridays, while for weekends, Sunday represents lighter traffic compared to Saturdays. The study derives continuous functions based on third-order polynomials using the Discrete Least Squares method to approximate velocities at each station. The results show that velocity approximation using continuous functions is more accurate on weekdays than weekends, indicating smoother traffic flow and less significant traffic congestion on weekends. The use of DLSM has provided an accurate polynomial model for approximating velocity, highlighting its usefulness in dealing with complex traffic patterns. Moreover, error calculations for continuous functions on both weekdays and weekends showed higher error compared to the piecewise continuous function, suggesting that continuous functions offer greater accuracy. Limitations include the scope of data collection being limited to a single bus route and a specific time. Hence, there is a need for more future comprehensive studies across different modes of transportation and schedules.

Keywords: velocity; error; compare.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Traveling in cities like Kuala Lumpur is challenging due to rapid urbanization and growing traffic congestion. Understanding travel patterns is crucial for effective transportation management (Afrin & Yodo, 2020). Factors such as distance, velocity, and time play a key role in analyzing these patterns, helping commuters and planners make informed decisions. Polynomial regression is a useful method for studying travel trends, as it captures complex relationships between variables by using

higher-degree functions instead of simple straight lines, making it more flexible than linear regression (Kotu & Deshpande, 2015). Distance refers to how far two locations are from each other and is a scalar quantity, meaning it has magnitude but no direction, unlike displacement, which includes both (Halliday et al., 2014). It can be measured using the Pythagorean theorem and varies based on context, such as travel distance (total path length) or Manhattan distance (applied in grid systems) (Mather & Koch, 2010). Understanding distance calculations is vital for applications in physics, navigation, and urban planning.

Velocity is the rate at which an object's position changes over time in a specific direction. Unlike speed, velocity is a vector quantity, meaning it includes both magnitude and direction. Its unit is meters per second (ms^{-1}) (ByJus, 2019). Changes in velocity indicate acceleration, whether by increasing speed, slowing down, or changing direction (Jones, 2019). Velocity analysis is fundamental in physics and engineering, helping predict motion and optimize transport efficiency. The Discrete Least Squares method is a mathematical approach used to approximate functions and fit data by minimizing the difference between predicted and actual values (Grisetti et al., 2020). It is widely applied in robotics, computer vision, and numerical analysis to improve accuracy. This method is particularly useful when data does not follow a clear pattern, allowing for reliable approximations even in complex scenarios. It is used in various fields, including engineering, physics, finance, and statistics, for solving real-world problems such as fluid dynamics and heat transfer (Weisstein, 2024).

Traffic congestion is a major issue, especially during weekday peak hours, leading to slower and inconsistent acceleration rates (Retallack & Ostendorf, 2019). Non-peak hours, such as late evenings and weekends, generally allow smoother traffic flow. However, weekend traffic is no longer as light as before, often resembling weekday rush hour (O'Fallon & Sullivan, 2011). These shifts in traffic trends require policymakers to adjust strategies for better traffic management. Weekend traffic patterns can also lead to increased accident risks due to higher speeds and unpredictable driving behaviors compared to weekday congestion (Yu & Abdel-Aty, 2013). Analyzing these differences helps transportation planners implement better safety measures, such as dynamic lane management on weekdays and speed control on weekends. Understanding these variations is essential for road safety and traffic optimization. Error measurement is crucial in evaluating velocity approximations, ensuring accuracy in predictions. Absolute error measures the direct difference between actual and approximated velocities, while relative error assesses the magnitude of error relative to the true value (Ford, 2015). Advanced techniques like Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) are widely used in model validation, with MAE often preferred for clarity (Karunasingha, 2021). Reducing errors enhances model reliability and improves real-world applications.

This study aims to compare velocity approximations of GOKL CityBus rides on weekdays and weekends using the Discrete Least Squares Method. Understanding variations in travel patterns caused by factors like congestion, route choices, and commuter behavior can provide valuable insights for transportation planning in Kuala Lumpur. More accurate velocity approximations can improve traffic management strategies, ultimately leading to a more efficient and safer urban transit system.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This section provides a detailed explanation of the methods and materials used in this study.

2.1 Step 1: Data Acquisition

Data on transportation locations and traffic conditions for both weekdays and weekends were collected using various sources. Research papers and articles from Google Scholar provided background information, while GPS tools and applications like Google Maps helped analyze

transportation options. The Strava app was used to accurately record time and distance for selected transport types.

The collected data included time and distance measurements from the starting to the endpoint of each stop. To ensure consistency, recorded time in minutes was converted to hours using the following equation:

$$Time (hours) = \frac{Time (minutes)}{60} \quad (1)$$

This conversion allowed velocity to be measured in kilometers per hour for accurate analysis.

2.2 Step 2: Find continuous and piecewise continuous function

This step involved deriving a continuous velocity function for weekdays and weekends using the Discrete Least Squares Method. The continuous function was based on all data points. To determine this function, a third-degree polynomial equation was applied using the Discrete Least Squares Method. This approach was used to accurately determine the coefficients of the polynomial equation. From these coefficients, the distance equation was derived by substituting them into the general polynomial equation, as shown in Equation (2).

$$f(x) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + a_3x^3 \quad (2)$$

A matrix equation was then constructed and solved to obtain the coefficients, as shown in Equation (3). Differentiating the distance function provided the velocity function.

$$\begin{bmatrix} n & \sum x & \sum x^2 & \sum x^3 \\ \sum x & \sum x^2 & \sum x^3 & \sum x^4 \\ \sum x^2 & \sum x^3 & \sum x^4 & \sum x^5 \\ \sum x^3 & \sum x^4 & \sum x^5 & \sum x^6 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sum y \\ \sum xy \\ \sum x^2y \\ \sum x^3y \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The matrix was solved using Maple to obtain the coefficients for a_0 , a_1 , a_2 and a_3 to formulate the polynomial function for distance, $f(x)$ as,

$$f(x) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + a_3x^3 \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) was differentiated with respect to x , where x represents time in hours, as,

$$f'(x) = \frac{d}{dx} (a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + a_3x^3) \quad (5)$$

The velocity function, $f'(x)$ was obtained as,

$$f'(x) = a_1 + 2a_2x + 3a_3x^2 \quad (6)$$

Finally, velocity was approximated by substituting time values into this function. The average velocity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\frac{\sum V}{n} \quad (7)$$

Graphs of these results were generated using Microsoft Excel.

2.3 Step 3: Comparison on performance analysis

The accuracy of velocity approximations was evaluated using Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for the continuous function. The function with the highest accuracy was identified by comparing errors during weekdays and weekends. The formulae for calculating exact velocity, absolute error, and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) are shown in Equations (8), (9), and (10), respectively.

$$Exact\ Velocity = \frac{Distance\ (km)}{Time\ (hours)} \quad (8)$$

$$Absolute\ Error = |Exact\ Velocity - Approximate\ Velocity| \quad (9)$$

$$MAE = \frac{\sum Absolute\ Error}{n} \quad (10)$$

The formula for calculating the difference and percentage error is shown in Equations (11) and (12). Graphical representations of the error analysis were created using Microsoft Excel.

$$Difference = Value_{Weekday} - Value_{Weekend} \quad (11)$$

$$Percentage\ Error = \left(\frac{Difference}{Value_{Weekday}} \right) \cdot 100\% \quad (12)$$

3. FINDINGS

The GOKL CityBus (GOKL-03-Red) operates on a circular route with 24 stops, starting and ending at Titiwangsa. The estimated travel time for the full route is 31 minutes. Service hours run from 6:00 a.m. to 11:00 p.m. on weekdays and 7:00 a.m. to 11:00 p.m. on weekends.

Data was collected at 1:00 p.m. on a weekday (Thursday) and a weekend (Sunday) to avoid peak traffic and ensure a fair comparison. Thursday was chosen for its stable weekday traffic, while Sunday was selected due to lower congestion than Saturday. This timing provided a clearer distinction between weekday and weekend conditions.

Figures illustrate the bus (Figure 1), its route (Figure 2), and schedule (Figure 3), while Table 1 lists all 24 stations.

Figure 1. GOKL CityBus (GOKL-03-(Red)).

Figure 2. GOKL CityBus (GOKL-03-(Red)) Route.

GOKL-03-(RED) bus Time Schedule	
Titiwangsa ↔ KL Sentral Route Timetable:	
Sunday	07:00 - 23:00
Monday	06:00 - 23:00
Tuesday	06:00 - 23:00
Wednesday	06:00 - 23:00
Thursday	06:00 - 23:00
Friday	06:00 - 23:00
Saturday	07:00 - 23:00

Figure 3. GOKL CityBus (GOKL-03-(Red) Time Schedule.

Table 1. GOKL CityBus (GOKL-03-(Red)) Stations.

No	Stations
1	Titiwangsa
2	Damai Service Hospital
3	Monorail Chow Kit
4	Pasar Chow Kit
5	Sri Amar
6	Pertama Complex
7	Globe KL
8	Laman Tunku Abdul Rahman
9	Dataran Merdeka
10	Dayabumi
11	KTM Kuala Lumpur
12	KL Sentral
13	1 Sentral
14	Muzium Negara
15	Masjid Negara
16	Dayabumi
17	Menara DBKL 2
18	Medan Mara
19	Wisma Sime Darby
20	Tiong Nam
21	Chow Kit
22	Grand Seasons Hotel
23	Hospital Kuala Lumpur
24	Titiwangsa

3.1 Location, Transportation and Data Acquisition

Kuala Lumpur was selected for this study due to its high traffic congestion, making it an ideal location for comparing velocity approximation on weekdays and weekends. Among various transportation modes, the bus was chosen as it follows a fixed route and schedule, ensuring consistency. The GOKL CityBus (GOKL-03-Red) route spans 24 stations from Titiwangsa to KL Sentral.

Data collection occurred at 1:00 p.m. on a weekday (Thursday) and a weekend (Sunday) to ensure comparability. The ‘Strava’ app was used to record travel time and distance between stations. Table 2 presents the collected data.

Table 2. Data Obtained on Weekday and Weekend.

No	Station	Weekday (Thursday)		Weekend (Sunday)	
		Time (minutes)	Distance (km)	Time (minutes)	Distance (km)
1	Titivangsa	13:00	0.00	13:00	0.00
2	Damai Service Hospital	13:01	0.31	13:02	0.31
3	Monorail Chow Kit	13:04	0.76	13:03	0.76
4	Pasar Chow Kit	13:06	1.03	13:06	1.03
5	Sri Amar	13:08	1.42	13:08	1.42
6	Pertama Complex	13:10	1.87	13:09	1.87
7	Globe KL	13:12	2.19	13:12	2.19
8	Laman Tunku Abdul Rahman	13:13	2.48	13:13	2.48
9	Dataran Merdeka	13:15	2.91	13:14	2.91
10	Dayabumi	13:17	3.45	13:16	3.45
11	KTM Kuala Lumpur	13:18	4.07	13:17	4.07
12	KL Sentral	13:21	5.29	13:19	5.29
13	1 Sentral	13:23	5.82	13:21	5.82
14	Muzium Negara	13:25	6.87	13:23	6.87
15	Masjid Negara	13:27	7.86	13:25	7.86
16	Dayabumi	13:28	8.29	13:26	8.29
17	Menara DBKL 2	13:31	9.04	13:27	9.04
18	Medan Mara	13:33	9.48	13:28	9.48
19	Wisma Sime Darby	13:35	9.99	13:29	9.99
20	Tiong Nam	13:36	10.32	13:30	10.32
21	Chow Kit	13:39	10.88	13:31	10.88
22	Grand Seasons Hotel	13:41	11.28	13:32	11.28
23	Hospital Kuala Lumpur	13:42	11.62	13:33	11.62
24	Titivangsa	13:43	12.12	13:34	12.12

To calculate velocity, time was converted from minutes to hours (time ÷ 60). Velocity was determined using:

$$Velocity = \frac{Distance (km)}{Time (hours)} \tag{13}$$

Tables 3 and 4 display the processed weekday and weekend data, respectively.

Table 3. Weekday Data.

No	Station	Time (minutes)	Accumulate Time (minutes)	Accumulate Time (hours)	Distance (km)
1	Titivangsa	0	0	0.0000000000	0.00
2	Damai Service Hospital	1	1	0.0166666667	0.31
3	Monorail Chow Kit	3	4	0.0666666667	0.76
4	Pasar Chow Kit	2	6	0.1000000000	1.03
5	Sri Amar	2	8	0.1333333333	1.42
6	Pertama Complex	2	10	0.1666666667	1.87
7	Globe KL	2	12	0.2000000000	2.19
8	Laman Tunku Abdul Rahman	1	13	0.2166666667	2.48
9	Dataran Merdeka	2	15	0.2500000000	2.91
10	Dayabumi	2	17	0.2833333333	3.45
11	KTM Kuala Lumpur	1	18	0.3000000000	4.07
12	KL Sentral	3	21	0.3500000000	5.29
13	1 Sentral	2	23	0.3833333333	5.82
14	Muzium Negara	2	25	0.4166666667	6.87
15	Masjid Negara	2	27	0.4500000000	7.86
16	Dayabumi	1	28	0.4666666667	8.29
17	Menara DBKL 2	3	31	0.5166666667	9.04
18	Medan Mara	2	33	0.5500000000	9.48
19	Wisma Sime Darby	2	35	0.5833333333	9.99
20	Tiong Nam	1	36	0.6000000000	10.32

21	Chow Kit	3	39	0.6500000000	10.88
22	Grand Seasons Hotel	2	41	0.6833333333	11.28
23	Hospital Kuala Lumpur	1	42	0.7000000000	11.62
24	Titiwangsa	1	43	0.7166666667	12.12

Table 4. Weekend Data.

No	Station	Time (minutes)	Accumulate Time (minutes)	Accumulate Time (hours)	Distance (km)
1	Titiwangsa	0	0	0.0000000000	0.00
2	Damai Service Hospital	2	2	0.0333333333	0.31
3	Monorail Chow Kit	1	3	0.0500000000	0.76
4	Pasar Chow Kit	3	6	0.1000000000	1.03
5	Sri Amar	2	8	0.1333333333	1.42
6	Pertama Complex	1	9	0.1500000000	1.87
7	Globe KL	3	12	0.2000000000	2.19
8	Laman Tunku Abdul Rahman	1	13	0.2166666667	2.48
9	Dataran Merdeka	1	14	0.2333333333	2.91
10	Dayabumi	2	16	0.2666666667	3.45
11	KTM Kuala Lumpur	1	17	0.2833333333	4.07
12	KL Sentral	2	19	0.3166666667	5.29
13	1 Sentral	2	21	0.3500000000	5.82
14	Muzium Negara	2	23	0.3833333333	6.87
15	Masjid Negara	2	25	0.4166666667	7.86
16	Dayabumi	1	26	0.4333333333	8.29
17	Menara DBKL 2	1	27	0.4500000000	9.04
18	Medan Mara	1	28	0.4666666667	9.48
19	Wisma Sime Darby	1	29	0.4833333333	9.99
20	Tiong Nam	1	30	0.5000000000	10.32

21	Chow Kit	1	31	0.5166666667	10.88
22	Grand Seasons Hotel	1	32	0.5333333333	11.28
23	Hospital Kuala Lumpur	1	33	0.5500000000	11.62
24	Titiwangsa	1	34	0.5666666667	12.12

3.2 Continuous Function for Velocity Approximation

Velocity approximation was conducted using a continuous function to assess accuracy via the Discrete Least Squares Method. A third-degree polynomial equation was used, ensuring a quadratic velocity function and a cubic distance function.

Time and distance data for weekdays and weekends were processed into summation tables. A matrix formulation was then constructed and solved using Maple to determine polynomial coefficients for the distance function, as shown in Equation (14).

$$f(x) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + a_3x^3 \tag{14}$$

Differentiating this equation with respect to time yielded the velocity function. All these steps are presented below.

3.2.1 Deriving Continuous Function

Summation tables for weekday and weekend were constructed.

Table 5. Continuous Function Summation Table for Weekday.

Accumulative Time (x)	Distance (y)	x ²	x ³	x ⁴	x ⁵	x ⁶	xy	x ² y	x ³ y
0.00000000	0.00	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000
0.01666666	0.31	0.0002	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.00516	0.00008	0.00000
0.06666666	0.76	0.0044	0.0002	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.05066	0.00337	0.00022
0.10000000	1.03	0.0100	0.0010	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	0.10300	0.01030	0.00103
0.13333333	1.42	0.0177	0.0023	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.18933	0.02524	0.00336
0.16666666	1.87	0.0277	0.0046	0.0007	0.0001	0.0000	0.31166	0.05194	0.00865
0.20000000	2.19	0.0400	0.0080	0.0016	0.0003	0.0000	0.43800	0.08760	0.01752
0.21666666	2.48	0.0469	0.0101	0.0022	0.0004	0.0001	0.53733	0.11642	0.02522
0.25000000	2.91	0.0625	0.0156	0.0039	0.0009	0.0002	0.72750	0.18187	0.04546
0.28333333	3.45	0.0802	0.0227	0.0064	0.0018	0.0005	0.97750	0.27695	0.07847

0.30000000 00	4.07	0.0900 000000	0.0270 000000	0.0081 000000	0.0024 300000	0.0007 290000	1.22100 00000	0.36630 00000	0.10989 00000
0.35000000 00	5.29	0.1225 000000	0.0428 750000	0.0150 062500	0.0052 521875	0.0018 382656	1.85150 00000	0.64802 50000	0.22680 87500
0.38333333 33	5.82	0.1469 444444	0.0563 287037	0.0215 926698	0.0082 771901	0.0031 729229	2.23100 00000	0.85521 66667	0.32783 30556
0.41666666 67	6.87	0.1736 111111	0.0723 379630	0.0301 408179	0.0125 586741	0.0052 327809	2.86250 00000	1.19270 83333	0.49696 18056
0.45000000 00	7.86	0.2025 000000	0.0911 250000	0.0410 062500	0.0184 528125	0.0083 037656	3.53700 00000	1.59165 00000	0.71624 25000
0.46666666 67	8.29	0.2177 777778	0.1016 296296	0.0474 271605	0.0221 326749	0.0103 285816	3.86866 66667	1.80537 77778	0.84250 96296
0.51666666 67	9.04	0.2669 444444	0.1379 212963	0.0712 593364	0.0368 173238	0.0190 222840	4.67066 66667	2.41317 77778	1.24680 85185
0.55000000 00	9.48	0.3025 000000	0.1663 750000	0.0915 062500	0.0503 284375	0.0276 806406	5.21400 00000	2.86770 00000	1.57723 50000
0.58333333 33	9.99	0.3402 777778	0.1984 953704	0.1157 889660	0.0675 435635	0.0394 004121	5.82750 00000	3.39937 50000	1.98296 87500
0.60000000 00	10.32	0.3600 000000	0.2160 000000	0.1296 000000	0.0777 600000	0.0466 560000	6.19200 00000	3.71520 00000	2.22912 00000
0.65000000 00	10.88	0.4225 000000	0.2746 250000	0.1785 062500	0.1160 290625	0.0754 188906	7.07200 00000	4.59680 00000	2.98792 00000
0.68333333 33	11.28	0.4669 444444	0.3190 787037	0.2180 371142	0.1489 920280	0.1018 112192	7.70800 00000	5.26713 33333	3.59920 77778
0.70000000 00	11.62	0.4900 000000	0.3430 000000	0.2401 000000	0.1680 700000	0.1176 490000	8.13400 00000	5.69380 00000	3.98566 00000
0.71666666 67	12.12	0.5136 111111	0.3680 879630	0.2637 963735	0.1890 540676	0.1354 887485	8.68600 00000	6.22496 66667	4.46122 61111
8.80000000 00	139.35	4.4061 111111	2.4797 222222	1.4872 294753	0.9274 800772	0.5936 895992	72.4160 000000	41.3912 388889	24.9703 569444

$$\begin{bmatrix} 24 & 8.800000000 & 4.406111111 & 2.479722222 \\ 8.800000000 & 4.406111111 & 2.479722222 & 1.4872294753 \\ 4.406111111 & 2.479722222 & 1.4872294753 & 0.9274800772 \\ 2.479722222 & 1.4872294753 & 0.9274800772 & 0.5936895992 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 139.35 \\ 72.41600000 \\ 41.39123889 \\ 24.97035694 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

After calculating the matrix in Equation (15), the coefficients are,

$$a_0 = 0.265268546547024$$

$$a_1 = 0.705144942380285$$

$$a_2 = 55.6353096724349$$

$$a_3 = -47.7299738122579$$

Substitute the coefficients in Equation (14), then the distance equation, $f(x)$ for continuous function during weekday is,

$$f(x) = 0.265268546547024 + 0.705144942380285x + 55.6353096724349x^2 - 47.7299738122579x^3 \quad (16)$$

Then, differentiate Equation (16),

$$f'(x) = \frac{d}{d(x)}(f(x)) \tag{17}$$

The velocity equation, $f'(x)$ for continuous function during weekday is,

$$f'(x) = 0.705144942380285 + 111.2706193x - 143.1899214x^2 \tag{18}$$

Similar calculations were performed for the weekend dataset, following the same process to determine the polynomial equations for velocity approximation.

The velocity equation, $f'(x)$ for continuous function during weekend is,

$$f'(x) = -0.644689751636494 + 126.1289857x - 131.0663664x^2 \tag{19}$$

These results provide insight into velocity trends for weekdays and weekends, allowing further analysis using the continuous method.

3.2.2 Velocity Approximation

The velocity was approximated for each station during both weekdays and weekends for continuous function. Table 6 presents the velocity approximation, and Figure 4 illustrates the corresponding graph.

Table 6. Velocity Approximation for Continuous Function.

WEEKDAY			WEEKEND		
Station	Time (hours)	Velocity (km/h)	Station	Time (hours)	Velocity (km/h)
Titiwangsa	0.0000000 000	0.70514494 2	Titiwangsa	0.0000000 000	- 0.64468975 2
Damai Service Hospital	0.0166666 667	2.51988028 6	Damai Service Hospital	0.0333333 333	3.41398047 6
Monorail Chow Kit	0.0666666 667	7.48678657 8	Monorail Chow Kit	0.0500000 000	5.33409361 7
Pasar Chow Kit	0.1000000 000	10.4003076 6	Pasar Chow Kit	0.1000000 000	10.6575451 5
Sri Amar	0.1333333 333	12.9956289 1	Sri Amar	0.1333333 333	13.8424396 1
Pertama Complex	0.1666666 667	15.2727503 4	Pertama Complex	0.1500000 000	15.3256648 6
Globe KL	0.2000000 000	17.2316719 5	Globe KL	0.2000000 000	19.3384527 3
Laman Tunku Abdul Rahman	0.2166666 667	18.0918078 1	Laman Tunku Abdul Rahman	0.2166666 667	20.5304193 9
Dataran Merdeka	0.2500000 000	19.5734296 8	Dataran Merdeka	0.2333333 333	21.6495714 1
Dayabumi	0.2833333 333	20.7368517 2	Dayabumi	0.2666666 667	23.6694314 9
KTM Kuala Lumpur	0.3000000 000	21.1992378 1	KTM Kuala Lumpur	0.2833333 333	24.5701395 6

KL Sentral	0.3500000 000	22.1090963 3	KL Sentral	0.3166666 667	26.1531117 6
1 Sentral	0.3833333 333	22.3179188 9	1 Sentral	0.3500000 000	27.4448253 6
Muzium Negara	0.4166666 667	22.2085416 3	Muzium Negara	0.3833333 333	28.4452803 7
Masjid Negara	0.4500000 000	21.7809645 4	Masjid Negara	0.4166666 667	29.1544767 9
Dayabumi	0.4666666 667	21.4478510 7	Dayabumi	0.4333333 333	29.3998530 3
Menara DBKL 2	0.5166666 667	19.9712109	Menara DBKL 2	0.4500000 000	29.5724146 2
Medan Mara	0.5500000 000	18.5890343 3	Medan Mara	0.4666666 667	29.6721615 6
Wisma Sime Darby	0.5833333 333	16.8886579 5	Wisma Sime Darby	0.4833333 333	29.6990938 5
Tiong Nam	0.6000000 000	15.9191448 2	Tiong Nam	0.5000000 000	29.6532115
Chow Kit	0.6500000 000	12.5333057	Chow Kit	0.5166666 667	29.5345145
Grand Seasons Hotel	0.6833333 333	9.87832983 3	Grand Seasons Hotel	0.5333333 333	29.3430028 5
Hospital Kuala Lumpur	0.7000000 000	8.43151696 6	Hospital Kuala Lumpur	0.5500000 000	29.0786765 5
Titivangsa	0.7166666 667	6.90515414 4	Titivangsa	0.5666666 667	28.7415356
Average Velocity Approximation		15.2164260 3	Average Velocity Approximation		22.2324669 5

Figure 4. Graph of Velocity Approximation for Continuous Function.

The weekday velocity starts at 0.71 km/h, peaks at 1 Sentral (22.32 km/h), then declines. The weekend velocity starts at -0.54 km/h (potential error), peaks at Wisma Sime Darby (29.70 km/h), and remains high. The average velocity is 15.22 km/h on weekdays and 22.23 km/h on weekends, suggesting smoother traffic flow on weekends. Weekend is more likely to have no traffic jams in between the stations as compared to the weekday in terms of velocities.

3.3 Performance Analysis Comparison Based on Error Determination

Velocity equations and approximations were obtained using continuous functions for both weekdays and weekends. This section calculates the error for the method. The exact velocity, absolute error, and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) were determined using:

$$Exact\ Velocity = \frac{Distance\ (km)}{Time\ (hours)} \tag{20}$$

$$Absolute\ Error = |Exact\ Value - Approximate\ Value| \tag{21}$$

$$MAE = \frac{\sum Absolute\ Error}{n} \tag{22}$$

3.3.1 Continuous Function for Weekday

Table 7 shows error calculations for weekdays, and Figure 5 illustrates the error graph.

Table 7. Error for Continuous Function during Weekday.

WEEKDAY					
Station	Time (hours)	Distance (km)	Exact Velocity (km/h)	Approximate Velocity (km/h)	Error
Titiwangsa	0.000000 0000	0.00	0.0000000000	0.705144942	0.70514 4942
Damai Service Hospital	0.016666 6667	0.31	18.6000000000	2.519880286	16.0801 1971
Monorail Chow Kit	0.066666 6667	0.76	11.4000000000	7.486786578	3.91321 3422
Pasar Chow Kit	0.100000 0000	1.03	10.3000000000	10.40030766	0.10030 7658
Sri Amar	0.133333 3333	1.42	10.6500000000	12.99562891	2.34562 8913
Pertama Complex	0.166666 6667	1.87	11.2200000000	15.27275034	4.05275 0342
Globe KL	0.200000 0000	2.19	10.9500000000	17.23167195	6.28167 1946
Laman Tunku Abdul Rahman	0.216666 6667	2.48	11.4461538462	18.09180781	6.64565 3968
Dataran Merdeka	0.250000 0000	2.91	11.6400000000	19.57342968	7.93342 968
Dayabumi	0.283333 3333	3.45	12.1764705882	20.73685172	8.56038 1132
KTM Kuala Lumpur	0.300000 0000	4.07	13.5666666667	21.19923781	7.63257 114
KL Sentral	0.350000 0000	5.29	15.1142857143	22.10909633	6.99481 0612
1 Sentral	0.383333 3333	5.82	15.1826086957	22.31791889	7.13531 0195
Muzium Negara	0.416666 6667	6.87	16.4880000000	22.20854163	5.72054 163
Masjid Negara	0.450000 0000	7.86	17.4666666667	21.78096454	4.31429 7877

Dayabumi	0.466666 6667	8.29	17.7642857143	21.44785107	3.68356 5352
Menara DBKL 2	0.516666 6667	9.04	17.4967741935	19.9712109	2.47443 6702
Medan Mara	0.550000 0000	9.48	17.2363636364	18.58903433	1.35267 0698
Wisma Sime Darby	0.583333 3333	9.99	17.1257142857	16.88865795	0.23705 6339
Tiong Nam	0.600000 0000	10.32	17.2000000000	15.91914482	1.28085 5182
Chow Kit	0.650000 0000	10.88	16.7384615385	12.5333057	4.20515 5843
Grand Seasons Hotel	0.683333 3333	11.28	16.5073170732	9.878329833	6.62898 7241
Hospital Kuala Lumpur	0.700000 0000	11.62	16.6000000000	8.431516966	8.16848 3034
Titivangsa	0.716666 6667	12.12	16.9116279070	6.905154144	10.0064 7376
Mean Absolute Error					5.26889 6555

Figure 5. Graph of Error for Continuous Function during Weekday.

The exact velocity fluctuates, peaking at 18.60 km/h at Damai Service Hospital, while the approximate velocity follows a smoother trend, peaking at 22.32 km/h at 1 Sentral. The smallest error (0.10 km/h) occurs at Pasar Chow Kit, while the largest error (16.08 km/h) is at Damai Service Hospital. The MAE is 5.27 km/h, indicating moderate approximation accuracy.

3.3.2 Continuous Function for Weekend

Table 8 shows error calculations for weekends, and Figure 6 illustrates the error graph.

Table 8. Error for Continuous Function during Weekend.

Station	Accumulate Time (hours)	Distance (km)	Exact Velocity (km/h)	Approximate Velocity (DLSM) (km/h)	Error
Titivangsa	0.0000000 000	0.00	0.0000000000	-0.644689752	0.644689 752
Damai Service Hospital	0.0333333 333	0.31	9.3000000000	3.413980476	5.886019 524
Monorail Chow Kit	0.0500000 000	0.76	15.2000000000	5.334093617	9.865906 383

Pasar Chow Kit	0.1000000 000	1.03	10.3000000000	10.65754515	0.357545 154
Sri Amar	0.1333333 333	1.42	10.6500000000	13.84243961	3.192439 606
Pertama Complex	0.1500000 000	1.87	12.4666666667	15.32566486	2.858998 193
Globe KL	0.2000000 000	2.19	10.9500000000	19.33845273	8.388452 732
Laman Tunku Abdul Rahman	0.2166666 667	2.48	11.4461538462	20.53041939	9.084265 548
Dataran Merdeka	0.2333333 333	2.91	12.4714285714	21.64957141	9.178142 836
Dayabumi	0.2666666 667	3.45	12.9375000000	23.66943149	10.73193 149
KTM Kuala Lumpur	0.2833333 333	4.07	14.3647058824	24.57013956	10.20543 368
KL Sentral	0.3166666 667	5.29	16.7052631579	26.15311176	9.447848 598
1 Sentral	0.3500000 000	5.82	16.6285714286	27.44482536	10.81625 393
Muzium Negara	0.3833333 333	6.87	17.9217391304	28.44528037	10.52354 124
Masjid Negara	0.4166666 667	7.86	18.8640000000	29.15447679	10.29047 679
Dayabumi	0.4333333 333	8.29	19.1307692308	29.39985303	10.26908 38
Menara DBKL 2	0.4500000 000	9.04	20.0888888889	29.57241462	9.483525 728
Medan Mara	0.4666666 667	9.48	20.3142857143	29.67216156	9.357875 845
Wisma Sime Darby	0.4833333 333	9.99	20.6689655172	29.69909385	9.030128 335
Tiong Nam	0.5000000 000	10.32	20.6400000000	29.6532115	9.013211 498
Chow Kit	0.5166666 667	10.88	21.0580645161	29.5345145	8.476449 98
Grand Seasons Hotel	0.5333333 333	11.28	21.1500000000	29.34300285	8.193002 846
Hospital Kuala Lumpur	0.5500000 000	11.62	21.1272727273	29.07867655	7.951403 82
Titivangsa	0.5666666 667	12.12	21.3882352941	28.7415356	7.353300 307
Mean Absolute Error					7.941663 651

Figure 6. Graph of Error for Continuous Function during Weekend.

The exact velocity peaks at 15.20 km/h at Monorail Chow Kit, while the approximate velocity follows a smoother increase, peaking at 29.70 km/h at Wisma Sime Darby. The smallest error (0.36 km/h) is at Pasar Chow Kit, and the largest error (10.82 km/h) is at 1 Sentral. The MAE is 7.94 km/h, indicating moderate approximation accuracy.

4. DISCUSSION

Table 9 compares velocity approximation errors for continuous functions on weekdays and weekends. The difference and percentage error calculations follow Equations (23) and (24).

$$Difference = Value_{Weekday} - Value_{Weekend} \tag{23}$$

$$Percentage\ Error = \left(\frac{Difference}{Value_{Weekday}} \right) \cdot 100\% \tag{24}$$

Table 9. Error Analysis for Velocity Approximation.

	Velocity Approximation	Difference	Percentage
Weekday	5.268896555	2.672767096	50.73%
Weekend	7.941663651		

For weekdays, the continuous function resulted in 5.2689, while the weekend continuous function resulted in 7.9417. This indicates that the calculated difference was 2.6728, with a percentage difference of 50.73%. This suggests that the mean absolute error in the weekday velocity approximation was 50.73% lower than that in the weekend approximation. Therefore, the accuracy of velocity approximation on weekdays was found to be lower compared to weekends.

For weekends, the continuous function resulted in 7.9417, whereas the weekday continuous function resulted in 5.2689. This indicates that the calculated difference was 2.6728, with a percentage difference of 50.73%. This suggests that the weighted mean absolute error in the weekend velocity approximation was 50.73% higher than that in the weekday approximation. Thus, in velocity approximation, the weekend provided more accurate results compared to weekdays.

5. CONCLUSION

This study successfully applied the Discrete Least Squares Method to analyse velocity approximation during weekday and weekend traffic in Kuala Lumpur, within the location from Titiwangsa to KL Sentral. A continuous function was examined, and it was observed that the traffic patterns change significantly between weekday and weekend. Therefore, there is more congestion and

lower average velocity on weekday, while weekend has a smoother flow but with fluctuations in velocity. The study also emphasized the importance of error computation methods in assessing how accurate the approximations were, like Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Weighted Mean Absolute Error (WMAE). The performance comparison demonstrated that for weekday, the continuous function resulted in an average error of 5.2689. Similarly, for weekend, the continuous function resulted in 7.9417.

From the results, the study has successfully achieved its objectives by obtaining traffic data, formulating a continuous function, and analyzing its accuracy based on error determination. Therefore, this study contributes valuable insights into the use of mathematical modeling for traffic analysis, which can aid in improving transportation planning and time management in busy cities like Kuala Lumpur.

Acknowledgments: The authors would like to express their gratitude to Universiti Teknologi MARA for providing the necessary resources and support for this study. Special thanks to all researchers, faculty members, and individuals who contributed their insights and expertise throughout this research. Additionally, we appreciate the assistance of data collection teams and transportation authorities for facilitating the study. Lastly, sincere appreciation goes to family and friends for their continuous encouragement and support.

References

- Afrin, T., & Yodo, N. (2020). A Survey of Road Traffic Congestion Measures towards a Sustainable and Resilient Transportation System. *Sustainability*, 12(11), 4660. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12114660>
- ByJus. (2019). *Velocity - Definition, Units, Formula, Examples, Equations*. ByJus. <https://byjus.com/physics/velocity/>
- Ford, W. (2015, January 1). *Chapter 8 - Floating Point Arithmetic* (W. Ford, Ed.). ScienceDirect; Academic Press. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/B9780123944351000089>
- Grisetti, G., Guadagnino, T., Aloise, I., Colosi, M., Della Corte, B., & Schlegel, D. (2020). Least Squares Optimization: From Theory to Practice. *Robotics*, 9(3), 51. <https://doi.org/10.3390/robotics9030051>
- Halliday, D., Resnick, R., & Walker, J. (2014). *Fundamentals of Physics Extended* (10th ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- Jones, A. Z. (2019, November 4). *What Velocity Means and How to Calculate It*. ThoughtCo. <https://www.thoughtco.com/velocity-definition-in-physics-2699021>
- Karunasingha, D. S. K. (2021). Root Mean Square Error or Mean Absolute Error? Use their ratio as well. *Information Sciences*, 585. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2021.11.036>
- Kotu, V., & Deshpande, B. (2015). Time Series Forecasting. *Predictive Analytics and Data Mining*, 305–327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-801460-8.00010-0>
- Mather, P. M., & Koch, M. (2010). *Computer Processing of Remotely-Sensed Images*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470666517>
- O'Fallon, C., & Sullivan, C. (2011). *Understanding and Managing Weekend Traffic Congestion*. https://australasiantransportresearchforum.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/2003_OFallon_Sullivan_c.pdf
- Retallack, A. E., & Ostendorf, B. (2019). Current Understanding of the Effects of Congestion on Traffic Accidents. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(18), 3400. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16183400>
- Weisstein, E. W. (2024). *Least Squares Fitting*. Mathworld.wolfram.com. <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/LeastSquaresFitting.html>
- Yu, R., & Abdel-Aty, M. (2013). Investigating the different characteristics of weekday and weekend crashes. *Journal of Safety Research*, 46, 91–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2013.05.002>